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DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY THROUGH YOGA EDUCATION
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Development of Personality through Yoga Education

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In this paper an effort has been made to shed light on the real meaning of yoga and Personality on the basis of Indian philosophy. The paper will promote a platform to identify one's self as well as it will clarify that Consciousness is the root of each and every individuals' personality development. Personality development from the modern perspective of Vedanta and yogic sciences highlights significant issues regarding personality development of modern human life. Concepts of pañcakoṣas and guṇas are very relevant in the context of understanding and developing one's personality. Eight-fold path of Patanjali has been described systematically for the use and practice of all concerned for attaining the real goal of human existence.

Key-Words : *Yoga, Personality, pañcakoṣ, Guṇas, Patañjali's aṣṭāṅga Yoga.*

Yoga is helping to evoke the hidden potentialities of man in a systematic and scientific way which man can become a fuller more complete individual. However, Personality is an important theme for each and every individual, from Yogic point of view, personality can be understood from a different perspective. Yoga views the person more deeply over and above physical body and mind; it has added a third entity called self (ātmā) or consciousness). A holistic personality comprises physical, emotional, intellectual, social and spiritual dimensions.

1. YOGA

The word 'Yoga' (means 'join' or 'unite') may be taken as the union of body, mind and soul, and is used in the literature both as an end as well as means. As an end, yoga signifies 'integration of personality' at the highest level. As means, yoga includes various practices and techniques which are employed to achieve the development of such integration.

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2. PERSONALITY

Etymologically the word personality derived from Latin word 'persona' which means Mask but now moreover, we cannot take personality as an equivalent word for outward appearance or behavior which will be very superficial. We cannot ignore the inner aspect of individual. Psychologically speaking, personality is all that a person is. It is the totality of one's behavior towards own-self as well as others. So definitely, the term personality signifies something deep than mere appearance or outward behavior.

According to Swami Vivekananda "your personality is the type of person you are, which is shown by way you behave, feel and think". How a person behaves, feels and thinks how he conducts himself in given set of circumstances is largely determined by the state of his self consciousness level.

3. DIMENSIONS OF PERSONALITY

Personality development is a multi-dimensional phenomenon. There are several dimensions which need to be integrated. Absence of any one dimension makes one's personality incomplete and lop-sided. For a holistic personality, the following dimensions are required to be integrated.

Each dimension has specific activities and processes which undergo certain changes. These changes normally take place in an orderly sequence, though there may be variations in their rate. It is important to note that all dimensions of personality are overlapping, inter-dependent, and intricately interwoven. A purely compartmentalized approach is not at all possible.

4. DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY THROUGH THE ESSENCE OF YOGA

Personality development is the real sense refers to deeper levels of person. It is therefore necessary to know our mind. Very often our mind rebels, for us to beat a retreat from our efforts at implementing our resolution book are open before us, and our eyes are open. But, the mind has wandering, thinking about some past events, or some future plans. According to the Bhagvad Gita, the undisciplined mind acts as our enemy, whereas a trained mind acts as our friend. So we need to have clear idea of the mechanism of our mind.

"I" consciousness appropriating to our self all physical and mental as I eat, I see, I hear, I am confused, etc is called Ahamkara or I consciousness

"Our" I is represented by the master of the chariot the body is the chariot and the buddhi the charioteer. The manas is sense organs like ear, skin, eyes, tongue and nose which are the five

windows in human being that give him or her the knowledge of the objects in the world. Important activity of the mind that concerns personality developments of our emotions. Emotions can be broadly classified into two types' attraction and repulsion. Love, admiration, aspiration, sympathy, joy, worship, pride and the like indicate attraction, hate, anger, fear, sorrow, jealousy, disgust, shame, etc are the nature of repulsion

Yoga views the person more deeply over and above physical body and mind; it has added a third entity called self (ātma). In Yoga, the concepts of ego, self, and consciousness have different connotations. Concepts of pañcakoṣas, guṇas and eight fold path of Patanjali are very relevant in the context of understanding and development of personality.

4.1. Pañcakoṣa :

The concept of Pañcakoṣa adopts a multi-dimensional approach to the understanding of personality and explains the person in an extensive manner. The concept of Pañcakoṣa is mentioned in the Taittirīya Upaniṣad.

The word, Pañcakoṣa comprises two words: pañca and koṣa. Pañca means five; and koṣa means body or sheath or layer. Thus, Pañcakoṣa literally means five bodies or five sheaths. According to the concept of Pañcakoṣa, the 'self' the divine spirit is the real identity of a person. It constitutes the inner most core of a person. This real identity is encased in a series of five koṣas (sheaths), named respectively from the outermost to the innermost as: Annamayakoṣa: (physical or gross body), Prāṇamayakoṣa (energy body), Manomayakoṣa (mental body), Vijñānamayakoṣa (wisdom body), and Ānandamayakoṣa (bliss). The absolute reality can be discovered through the experience of the 'self'

These koṣas represent functioning of a person at different levels (Rama et al, 1976). They carry different levels of awareness; and are arranged successively from the grosser to increasingly more subtle awareness. Here, annamayakoṣa is the grossest body; while Ānandamayakoṣa is the most subtle body of awareness. Each sheath covers and obscures the more subtle awareness of the body which is interior to it. This implies that a person functions at various levels of awareness. It is important for you to note that all koṣas exist in a fixed order, but they are interrelated and form one entity. Therefore, the practices that benefit one

koṣa will benefit other koṣas also, and 'Self' can be accessed by working on all these bodies. **Annamayakoṣa:** Annamayakoṣais the outer-most body. This part is mainly nourished by the food (anna) which we take; hence is called annamayakoṣa. This body functions on physical plane. It represents the physical body which is measurable by physical means. This koṣa is constituted by the organs and systems of our body which we can understand with the help of anatomy and physiology.

It is essential that we keep this body healthy since only a healthy physical body can facilitate functioning of other koṣas (bodies or sheaths). Internal cleansing practices (ṣaṭkarma) and yogāsanas are main practices for development of physical body (Nagarathna, 2005). Āsanas are an effective means to attain flexibility, relaxation, strength, toning, balance and general fitness of annamayakoṣa (Vivekānanda, 2005).

Prāṇamayakoṣa: Prāṇamayakoṣas encased in the physical body and has the same form as the physical body. This koṣa consists of Prāṇa (the vital energy) which is crucial for life. We are alive because of this koṣa. Life is derived from this body; and our sense organs - eyes, ears, tongue, nose, and skin - perform their functions through this body.

Prāṇamayakoṣas the basis of our physical body. We all know that without prāṇa, the physical body becomes lifeless. This koṣa is constituted by nāḍis, cakras and various types of prāṇas (Udāna, prāṇa, Samāna, Apāna and Vyāna). prāṇa (energy) flows through the nāḍis (energy-channels). Our physical sheath is affected by this koṣa. This body is the link between annamayakoṣa (physical body) and manomayakoṣa (mental body).

Manomayakoṣa: It lies interior to the prāṇamayakoṣa (energy body). This koṣa is concerned with our emotional and cognitive behaviour which includes feelings, emotion, instincts, desires and various needs like security and protection from danger. Our emotions such as love, hate, fear, sadness, anger, disgust all are related to this koṣa.

In addition to this, manomayakoṣa also consists of manas, ahaṁkāra, memory and lower levels of buddhi or intelligence. The empirical knowledge, thinking and reasoning both inductive and deductive are part of this koṣa. Here, buddhi (intelligence) may yield to the pressure of emotions and habits; or it may make decision independent of the impulses or past programmes.

Our responses to the inputs received by the senses are controlled by this koṣa only (Vivekananda, 2005). Manomayakoṣa helps 'manas' (mind) to reach better decisions with rational thinking in handling day to day activities (Rama et al, 1976). At this level, one tends to draw conclusions on the basis of evidence and reasoning in day-to-day life. In short, it can be said that manomayakoṣa is concerned with our functioning at emotional level as well at lower levels of buddhi.

This koṣa is very significant as most of our day-to-day activities are governed by manomayakoṣa. If a person is impulsive, cannot control her/his emotions, then the person needs to work on this koṣa to improve on emotional dimension of her/his personality. This koṣa is the link between prāṇamayakoṣa (energy body) and vijñānamayakoṣa (intellectual body). This koṣa or body can be studied by focusing the attention inward on the

working of mind. By regulating the breath, mind can be brought into focus. Meditation and devotional sessions can be used to develop this koṣa (Nagarathna, 2005). This koṣa can be made healthy by expressing our negative emotions like anger, hate, fear etc. and also through constructive channels such as music, sports and games, stories, articles etc.

vijñānamayakoṣa : It lies interior to the manomayakoṣa. It consists of higher level of 'buddhi' which is related to power of discrimination and true understanding about the self. This koṣa does not give in to the passions of the other bodies (Rama et al, 1976). This is a realm of pure buddhi. This level is beyond thinking and reasoning. At this level, buddhi remains unaffected by emotions, habits, sense-impressions, perceptions or personal gains and egoism. It is governed by wisdom and viveka (which discriminates between right and wrong). If a person is able to discriminate between right and wrong, then the person can be said to be working at the level of the vijñānamayakoṣa.

The vijñānamayakoṣa establishes the link between manomayakoṣa (mental body) and ānandamayakoṣa (bliss body). We can access this koṣa by working upon three lower koṣas by removing their blockages and reducing our identification with them. Another way is by doing good activities and by associating ourselves with the people who are working at higher levels like thinkers, joyous people, yogīs etc. Exploring new avenues, learning more, and accomplishing good deeds etc. help to develop it (Vivekananda, 2005). This koṣa may be developed by analysing and understanding the problems in Yogic way (Nagarathna, 2005).

Ānandamayakoṣa : Ānandamayakoṣa is the most subtle body. It remains in the most intimate contact with pure spirit or the 'ātmā' which is the true reality of all of us. Ānandamayakoṣa reflects the blissful state of the 'self' characterised by an ineffable experience of peace, love and ecstasy. This koṣa can be functional in people who are dominated by selfless love. A person, functioning at this level, remains in a state of joy. S/he does not get affected by external stimuli or events or things. The individual at this stage remains in a perfect state of mental equipoise transcending even the Buddhi. Rationality or empirical experiences have no meaning for an individual in the bliss state.

We are generally not able to access this koṣa because we are entangled in the lower levels of functioning and are associated with other outer koṣas (Vivekananda, 2005). This koṣa can be accessed by practising joy in all circumstances and by doing niṣkāmakarma. (Nagarathna, 2005) If we think deeply we find that all the five bodies are important for a holistic personality. If we want to develop the 'self' - the core of the personality all bodies need to be integrated and given enough care and attention. In Section 1.4 of this Unit, we shall discuss various dimensions of holistic or integrated personality. You can see that the concept of Pañcakoṣa represents all those dimensions and emphasizes the integration of all five bodies for development of a holistic personality.

4.2. Guṇas (attributes): sattva-guṇa, rajas-guṇa and tamas-guṇa

Yoga also describes an individual human being on the basis of 'guṇas' or attributes. 'Guṇas' may be described as the qualities or the tendencies within a person which determine and

explain the personality and behaviour of a person. There are three guṇas - sattva, rajas, and tamas. Together they are known as tri-guṇa. These guṇas get reflected in our mental states and manifest behaviour.

prakāśa-kriyā-sthitiśīlambhutendriyātmakarāmbhogāpavargārthamdrśyam

The Bhagvadgītā also defines these guṇas in the similar way. According to the Bhagvadgītā, sattva is stainless (pure), luminous, and healthy. It is attached to happiness and knowledge (Bhagvadgītā, 14.6). Rajas is passion and arises due to attachment with worldly things. It binds an individual to the fruits of her/his actions (Bhagvadgītā, 14.7). Tamas is inertia which arises from ignorance (Bhagvadgītā, 14.8).

On the basis of above

description, we can simply say that sattva is associated with such qualities as brightness, kindness, intelligence, love, compassion for others etc. All these qualities reflect the 'selflessness' and egolessness within the person. Rajas can be said to be associated with activity, energy, passion, desires etc., whereas tamas is characterized by laziness, dullness, heaviness, ignorance, etc.

On the basis of the dominance of the above guṇas, an individual's personality can be categorised in three broad groups namely, sāttvika personality, rājasika personality, and tāmasika personality. These are the three types of personalities according to Yoga.

Sāttvika personality : is dominated by sāttvikaguṇa and has inherent desire to be good and caring. Here, behaviour is motivated by moral strength, respect for humanity, non-violence, meditation, kindness, silence, self-control, and purity of character (Srivastava, 2012). Forgiveness, patience, love and compassion for others, cool, altruistic behaviour etc. are some of the qualities of sattvaguṇa. According to the Bhagvadgītā (14:11), an individual endowed with sattvaguṇa becomes illuminated by wisdom. Asāttvika person becomes attached to happiness and can discriminate between right and wrong (Prabhupada, 1986). Renunciation and detachment are the characteristics of the personality of a person dominated by sattva. If a person works for others without his/her own interest, we can say that s/he is dominated by this guṇa. Sainly persons are an example of this type of personality.

If you look around in the society, you will find many great personalities who do lot of social

work. They selflessly serve disabled people, socially discarded women and children, children who have no parents and relatives to take care of. These are acts of pure love and compassion. Those who do such kind of work have no self interest. They are just a few or handfuls. They can do so since they have predominance of sattvaguṇa.

Rājasika personality : is dominated by action. According to the Bhagvadgītā (14.12), arājasika person becomes passion-oriented with desires and intense endeavour. Such a person gets attached to the activities which would lead to expected results (Prabhupada, 1986). The attachment with self-interest gives the person a distorted picture of right and wrong. Enthusiasm, interest, activity are some of the attributes of this guṇa (Srivastava, 2012). A person dominated by rajas remains active. This type of personality can be seen in the people who are always active to fulfil their desires. A person who is always aspiring and tirelessly working to fulfil those aspirations can be said to have arājasika personality. People with high achievement, motivation and with a vibrant attitude are the examples of this type of personality.

Tāmasika personality : is dominated by inertia (Bhagvadgītā, 14.13). This kind of person is characterised by inactivity, heedlessness, delusions, lack of enlightenment (Śāstri, 1982). Tamas produces ambiguity, idleness and fantasy. Tāmasika person derives happiness from self-delusion and miscomprehension (Srivastava, 2012). Procrastination, laziness, gossiping, day-dreaming, harming others, being revengeful etc. are some other characteristics of this guṇa. This kind of person remains aloof and does not care for others. A person who spends most of the time in gossiping, always sits idle and does not do anything worthwhile is an example of this type personality. Criminals or people who harm others are also examples of this personality type.

The above categorisation is based mainly on the dominance of a single guṇa. But, in real life, pure sātṭvika, rājasika, or tāmasika personalities are a rare phenomenon. Generally people have the combination of two or more guṇas and are dominated by more than one guṇa. In that case, personality can be put into different categories such as sātṭvika-rājasika, rājasika-tāmasika, etc. Individual difference can be explained by the variations in the degree of the sattva, rajas, and tamas within these combinations.

As a matter of fact, we all have sattva, rajas and tamas within us, which are reflected in different kinds of our mental states, tendencies, and actions at different times. We have sātṭvikatendency when we are helping others without our own interest. We are driven by rājasikatendency when we are doing our work in school, college, office or in home for expected results. Similarly, we show tamas when we are sleeping or while away the time.

4.3. Patañjali's Aṣṭāṅga Yoga for personality development

Aṣṭāṅga Yoga is a Yogic system that has been devised by Maharṣi Patañjali in order to control the mind. Aṣṭāṅga Yoga was enunciated basically for spiritual development, but it is also very relevant to attain holistic personality. Aṣṭāṅga Yoga, if adopted properly would help in physical, intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual development of a person.

It consists of eight components; therefore, it is known as Aṣṭāṅga-Yoga (eight-limbed Yoga). The components/limbs mentioned in Aṣṭāṅga Yoga are: Yama, Niyama, Āsana, Prāṇāyāma, Pratyāhāra, Dhāraṇā, Dhyāna and Samādhi. These eight components have been further divided into two parts known as Bahiraṅga Yoga and Antaraṅga Yoga. Bahiraṅga Yoga consists of Yama, Niyama, Āsana, Prāṇāyāma and Pratyāhāra; while Antaraṅga Yoga consists of last three limbs-Dhāraṇā, Dhyāna and Samādhi

Yama: *Ahiṃsā-satya-asteya-brahmacarya-aparigrahāḥ-yamāḥ*

Yama can be interpreted as self-restraints or the social code of conduct, which are to be followed in social life. Ahiṃsā (non-violence), Satya (truthfulness), Asteya (non-stealing), Brahmacharya (continence) and aparigraha (non-acquisitiveness) are yamas.

Yamas are very important. They tell us how we should behave in our social life. Ahiṃsā means not harming others in any manner - through intention, speech or action. Truthfulness means we should be truthful and honest in our thoughts and actions. Asteya means non-stealing which is opposite to stealing. Asteya includes not taking or using the things belonging to others without their permission. Brahmacharya means exercising control in our sexual behaviour. Aparigraha means that we should not accumulate or hoard things property/wealth etc, which are not required. If we analyse them in depth, we would find that the behaviour guided by these principles will help to control our emotions, promote our relations and would also lead towards spiritual path.

We all know that social problems like murders, corruption, theft, polygamy, rape etc. are caused by the violent tendencies, dishonesty, untruthfulness, greed, hoarding, stealing and sexual urges. If we exercise control on these, the society will be peaceful and our interpersonal relations will be good. In addition to this, yamas also bring emotional balance and mental peace and lead us to the spiritual journey. Thus, with the help of Yama, emotional, social and spiritual development is facilitated.

Niyama: *Śauca-santoṣa-tapaḥ-svādhyāya-īśvara-praṇidhānāni-niyamāḥ*

Five niyamas are: śauca (purity cleanliness), Santoṣa (contentment), Tapaḥ (austerity to

discipline body mind), Svādhyāya (study of self by introspection and studying scriptures), and Īśvara-praṇidhāna (surrender to God). Niyama can be viewed as observances or code of conduct in personal life.

The niyama of śauca implies that our body and our surroundings should be clean and mind should be pure. Santoṣa means that we should be contented with what we have in life and should not hanker after more and more; such cravings would lead to frustrations in life. The niyama of tapaḥ implies that we should discipline our body and mind by developing a habit of austerity; it will protect us from unnecessary extravagance for satisfying never-ending desires. Svādhyāya means the study of self and study of scriptures. It can be promoted by introspection and self-analysis. By Svādhyāya we can develop an insight into our behaviour, to know about our weaknesses and strengths. This will guide our behaviour and protect us from our wrong doings. Practising niyama in day-to-day life promotes emotional stability, knowledge about the 'self' and a sense of right and wrong; thus facilitating emotional, intellectual and spiritual development of oneself. Yama and niyama put together, thus, help to promote social, emotional, intellectual and spiritual development of an individual.

Āsana: Sthira-sukham-āsanam

Patañjali defines āsana as the steady and comfortable position (of the body). He does not talk about any specific āsanās. It is the Haṭha Yoga tradition in which various body-postures have been suggested by the proponents of Haṭha Yoga. Āsana helps to regulate the prāṇika flow in the body facilitating the functioning of various systems and organs of the body. Thus, āsanās help to promote physical development. Alongside, they also help regulation of emotions by working upon autonomic nervous system.

Prāṇāyāma : Tasmin satiśvāsa-praśvāsayor-gativicchedaḥprāṇāyāmaḥ

Prāṇāyāma means control and regulation of breathing process. Practising Prāṇāyāma helps in physical development by improving capacity and functioning of lungs. They help in emotional development by activating the parasympathetic system of the CNS (Central Nervous System). The activation of parasympathetic system makes a person relaxed. Regular practice of Prāṇāyāma makes a person energetic and relaxed. Thus Prāṇāyāma works not only at physical level, it also helps in emotional management. Our negative emotions like anger can be effectively managed by Prāṇāyāma.

Pratyāhāra : Sva-viśaya-asamprayogecitta-svarūpānukāraivendriyāṇāṃpratyāhāraḥ

Patañjali, in the above sūtra, defines Pratyāhāra as withdrawal of senses from their respective objects and experiences. It is related to control of senses.

Actually, our senses play a crucial role in our mental states and actions. We receive various inputs from our senses (seeing, hearing, smelling, touching and tasting). These inputs affect our mind and may make it agitated. For example, if we see a movie full of violence, our mind gets affected accordingly. As a result, for the whole day we may not be able to focus on our work as the violent scenes of the movie are disturbing us again and again. This kind of situation would not have aroused, had we not seen that violent movie. So in order to control the mind, sensations are to be withdrawn. This withdrawal (pratyāhāra) protects us from

emotional turbulences which are caused by continuous worldly inputs. However, it is not always possible to stop the inputs. In that case, pratyāhāra can be exercised by taking right inputs from our senses. The right selection of our inputs would protect our mind from undesirable states. Thus, pratyāhāra helps in emotional management.

Pratyāhāra can be done with the help of self-analysis and introspection. During introspection and self-analysis, we focus our attention within. It helps to make an inward journey. It makes the person aware of her/his strengths and weaknesses and leads her/him towards self-improvement. Thus, pratyāhāra helps a person in her/his emotional, intellectual and spiritual development.

Dhāraṇā : *Deśabandhas-cittasyadhāraṇā*

Dhāraṇā means fixing up of mind on a particular object as Patañjali says in the above sūtra. Dhāraṇā helps to improve concentration and stabilizes the mind. Thus, it helps in emotional, intellectual and spiritual development.

Dhyāna : *Tatrapratyayaikatānātādhyānam*

Dhyāna means an unbroken or uninterrupted flow of citta towards the object of contemplation. In simple words, it is the prolonged dhāraṇā. The practice of Dhyāna promotes the concentration and may lead towards emotional, intellectual and spiritual development in a person.

Samādhi : *Tadevārthamātra-nirbhāsamsvarūpa-śūnyamivasamādhiḥ*

Samādhi is that state of dhyāna in which the subject-object distinction is submerged. It is the final stage of Yoga. Samādhi leads to the state of self-realization. In this state, the object of dhyāna becomes more vivid and the awareness about one's own existence disappears. In this state, all emotions go away, and the individual is led towards inner peace, happiness and complete bliss. It is an increased state of concentration. In this state, mind appears as if not functioning but it is not blank. This state is characterised by the increased level of consciousness about the 'self'. 'Samādhi', therefore, would certainly contribute to emotional, intellectual and spiritual development of one's personality.

Dhāraṇā, dhāyana and samādhi, together called 'Samyama' are beneficial for one's intellectual, emotional and spiritual development.

Astanga Yoga and corresponding developmental dimensions of personality

Limbs of Aṣṭāṅga Yoga	Developmental Dimensions of Personality
<i>Yama</i>	Emotional, Social and Spiritual Development
<i>Niyama</i>	Emotional, Intellectual and Spiritual Development
<i>Āsana</i>	Physical and Emotional Development
<i>Prāṇāyāma</i>	Physical and Emotional Development
<i>Pratyāhāra</i>	Emotional, Intellectual and Spiritual Development
<i>Dhāraṇā, Dhyāna and Samadhi</i>	Emotional, Intellectual and Spiritual Development

5. CONCLUSION

Through the discussion we may realize that all the path like Pancakosa, Triguna, Patanjali's eight fold path all are leads to the consciousness. After long discussion it is clear that, in personality development the inner aspect of an individual is more important than outer aspect. It will be clearer through twodefinition of renowned personality psychologist Allport. Allport defined personality firstly in 1937 when he emphasis on outer adjustment of an individual as "Personality is the dynamic organization within the individual of those psychophysical systems that determine his unique adjustments to the environment" but after 24 years in 1961 he may realized that the inner development is most important matter in personality development so he redefined as "Personality is the dynamic organization within the individual of those psychophysical systems that determine his characteristics behavior and thought" This second definition is may not tacitly accepted by personality psychologists but it is more relevant to the present researcher. Whereas the inner aspect of an individual is nothing but his/her Consciousness level. The Consciousness is the root of any kind of personality. The level of consciousness may determine the level of personality development so now need not to say again the yogic principles are the best path to the development of integrated personality. So, just know own self through yoga and identify your consciousness level clearly, present researcher promises it will surely promote a great personality. Consciousness, Consciousness and Consciousness it is the totality for your integrated development.

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